

Proposal for Palm Oil Mill Effluent (POME) Treatment at Source to reclaim water

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Abstract: Malaysia is the largest producer and exporter of palm oil. The serious problems in the palm fruit processing are the managing of the wastewater generated during the processes. The wastes consist of a significant amount of solid wastes and a wastewater called palm oil mill effluent (POME). POME is a thick brownish liquid that contains high amount of total solids (40,500 mg/L), oil and grease (4000 mg/L), This highly polluting effluent is becoming a major problem to environment as if it not being treated well before discharged based on standard limit imposed by The Malaysian Department of Environment for effluent discharged. The main purpose of this work is to study the effective evaluate POME treatment at source as to reclaim water during propose design using vacuum drying and flash drying, by using steam ejector.

Keywords: Palm Oil Mill Effluent, Treatment, reclaim water.

Introduction

The annual production of palm oil worldwide is 58 million tons, planted over 14 million hectares (FAO, 2014). Oil palm is the most efficient oil-bearing crop in the world. It can produce up to 3.8 tons of oil per hectare, which is 9 times more than soya and 6 times more than sunflower (Marti, 1999). Because of its low production cost, palm oil is the most consumed vegetable oil. It is found in about half of all packaged products sold in supermarkets from the biscuit to the soap aisle (Spinks, 2014). Malaysia and Indonesia are producing 86 % of the total palm oil production worldwide (FAO, 2014). Currently, these countries are reaching a land limitation, which guides the focus of the oil palm industry to new continents, like Africa and South America. Although oil palm originated from West Africa, the production of the continent is minimal with only 2 million tons per year, which corresponds to 4 % of world production of palm oil (FAO, 2014). However, Africa possesses a lot of non-cultivated lands that constitute a huge potential to plant more palm trees.

Moreover, Oily Wastewater: Over the recent years, there has been an increasing concern for environmental risk of industrial activities associated with extraction, hydrocarbons, food processing transportations, and refining. These industries have increased the threat of oil pollution to the environment and subsequently, concomitant discharged into the natural environment creates major ecological problem throughout the world.

The concentration of oil in effluents from different industrial sources can be as high as 40,000mg/l (Arcadio & Gregoria, 2003). Unlike free or floating oil spilled in the sea, lakes or rivers, most of the industrial wastewaters contain oil-in-water emulsions among other basic contaminants. Emulsified oil in wastewater can lead to severe problems in different treatment stages. Oil in wastewaters has to be removed in order to.

- a) Prevent interfaces in water treatment units
- b) Reduce fouling in process equipment
- c) Avoid problems in biological treatment stages
- d) Comply with water discharge requirements.

The treatment of these wastes has been addressed by several techniques (a) chemical stabilization by addition of organic and inorganic compounds (b) adsorption.

Malaysia's total oil palm planted area in 2008 expanded by 4% or 183,000 hectares. The total planted area in the country was at 4.49 million hectares against 4.30 million hectares in 2007. The expansion in oil palm area continued to be concentrated in the state of Sarawak while in the Peninsular and Sabah planted area recorded only marginal increases (Malaysian Palm Oil Association, 2008)

Problem Statement

Palm Oil processing gives rise to polluting waste-water, known as Palm Oil Mill Effluent (POME) this waste-water then kept in disposal pond. The water could contain disease-causing pathogen or infectious agents like bacteria and viruses it also can cause serious unpleasant odour problems around the surrounding area due to high nitrogenous and phosphate content, increasing the production of oil palm will cause an

increase in water usage, thus needing better treatment methods to treat POME. Most research work looks at treating the POME to overcome the problems mentioned above.

Research Objectives

In our research work, we attempt to evaluate POME treatment at the source so as to reclaim water.

- i. Study to potential POME treatment for the major goal of reclaiming water at the source.
- ii. Investigate the feasibility of the proposed process.

Scope of the research project work

- i. Study the characteristics of POEM produced.
- ii. Study ways of separating water from other POEM.
- iii. Propose a potential water separation process.

Methodology

We will investigate the two major elements of this project:

- i. Mechanical Engineering Element for flash drying and condensate.
- ii. Equipment.

Reclaiming the water

To reclaim good water from the palm oil residuals process which produces unwanted water in which we will process it in a condensation phase to reclaim water useful for certain applications. It will employ mechanical engineering integration system to produce beneficial water utilization for perhaps irrigation or even drinking water usage.

Solid waste generation

In 2003, Malaysia crude palm oil industry produced 0.7 million ton palm oil per year. Crude palm oil production generates large amounts of process residues such as fibres (0.6 million ton per year), shell (0.2 million ton per year), and empty fruit bunches, EFB, (0.9 million ton per year). These residues such as EFB and shells are already reused/recycled as solid fuel. However, there are also other potential options to use these residues as a more valuable product. These options are reviewed in the next section. For wastes, which are currently disposed of such as decanter sludge and other more sustainable solutions for are also discussed based on recent research in Malaysia.

Table 1: the Average Values of Raw Material and Waste Generation from Five Selected Factories in Malaysia

	Wet weight (ton/ha/year)	Dry weight (ton/ha/year)
Fresh fruit bunch	16.5	10.6
Oil yield	2.75	2.75
Oil content in oil palm fruit (%)	17	–
Oil extraction (%)	16.8	–
Empty fruit bunch	3.96	2.6
Fiber	2.31	1.6
Shell	1.0	0.9
Wastewater	10.56	0.64

Water quantities used

A crude palm oil mill uses substantial quantities of water in the production process. Canal water is the water supply source. The average water consumption is 1.26 m³ /ton FFB. A detailed overview of water usage in the five selected factories is shown in Table 2.6 The water consumption per ton FFB does not differ much between the five crude palm oil factories due to the fact that most of the water is used as boiler water and turbine cooling water. Cooling water for the turbine is recycled in the production process for cleaning machines and domestic purposes. It has been estimated that in the year 2002 the crude palm oil industry in Malaysia consumed about 5 million m³ of water

Table 2: Water Sages and Wastewater Generation at 5 Selected Crude Palm Oil Mills

Factory	FFB (ton/day)	Water input (m ³ /ton FFB)			Wastewater (m ³ /ton FFB)
		Total	Boiler	Production & cooling water	
A	359	1.2	0.76	0.50	0.59
B	387	1.0	0.47	0.53	0.51
C	530	1.1	0.54	0.56	0.58
D	1650	1.3	0.51	0.75	0.54
E	223	1.3	0.75	0.55	1.03

Wastewater generation

In the wet process operation, large quantities of water are utilized during the extraction of crude palm oil. Results from a survey show that the water consumption in the production process is in the range of 1.0-1.3 m³ / ton FFB. About 53-79 % of the used water ends as palm oil mill effluents (POME). The other part is lost as steam, mainly through exhaust gases from the sterilizer. The total pollution load of biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), suspended solids (SS), oil, total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN) and total phosphorus (TP) in the process wastewater for the five selected factories is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Pollution Load from The five Selected Crude Palm Oil Factories

Factory	Water consumption (m ³ /ton FFB)	Wastewater (m ³ /ton FFB)	Pollution load from production source (kg /ton FFB)				
			BOD	SS	OIL	TKN	TP
A	1.2	0.56	30.7	18.2	2.5	0.6	0.02
B	1.0	0.51	20.3	19.9	3.9	0.1	0.01
C	1.1	0.58	29.1	21.6	3.7	0.2	0.05
D	1.3	0.54	25.1	15.1	6.6	0.5	Not detected
E	1.3	1.03	43.1	30.3	6.5	0.2	Not detected

The estimated pollution load from the entire crude palm oil industry in Malaysia can be summarized as follows:

- Wastewater generation 2.6 million m³ / year
- Oil loss in wastewater 10,400 ton/ year
- BOD in wastewater 77,220 ton/year
- SS in effluent 79,900 ton/ year
- TKN in effluent 2,600 ton/ year

Palm oil mill effluents (POME) as in the Figure 2.20

Figure 1: Raw POME (brownish in color)

Flash drying

High rates of evaporation in flash dryers are leading to low temperatures of the dried material and indicate that flash dryers are particularly useful for drying granular, crystalline, pasty, and powdery products.

Our Proposed design

In this chapter, a cost effective FFB system integration and installation are designed that can be implemented at a palm oil mill. The system integration is formed by installing a flash dryer at the output of the sterilizer which will function to perform flash drying of POME as the output of sterilizer and possibly to reclaim water out of this POME, so for our thinking, we going to propose the design using vacuum drying and Flash drying.

Design Parameters

The following design parameters were used for the design for the flash dryer and vacuum drying system integration:

- 1) 30 ton of FFB was applied as an input to the sterilizer chamber.
- 2) The temperature that was applied is 120 degree
- 3) The pressure that was applied is 2 bars

Figure 1: the design using vacuum drying and flash drying

The Palm Oil Mill Effluent (POME) 67% so the ratio is divided into 100. It will be $(67\% / 100) = 0.67$. So POME is going to be $(0.67 \times 30 \text{ ton/h}) = 20 \text{ ton/h}$ of POME

The following relationships are the parameters that were determined as the process responses in this study.

Flow Rate of the water $Q = \text{Volume} / \text{Time}$

Where Q flow rate the standard sized mills processing 30tonnes/hour of fruit bunches normally produce 10tonnes/hour of steam and design it will handle 20 ton/h of POME

So I am going to use 30ton of FFB we use this for design, so POME approximately 20 ton/h than the design capacity is 20ton/h as we assume.

Where V is volume flow water in min

$$\frac{20 \text{ ton/h}}{60 \text{ second}} \text{ It will be } = 333 \text{ liters /mint}$$

Where V flow water in the second

$$= \frac{20 \text{ ton/h}}{60 \text{ min} \times 60 \text{ second}} = (6 \text{ liters/second} \times \frac{1 \text{ kg}}{\text{liters}}) = 6 \text{ kg/second}$$

Saturated steam - low pressure - is common for heating services and secondary process pipes. Saturated steam - high pressure - is common in powerhouse; boiler and main process lines superheated steam is common in power generation and turbine plants.

The steam velocities assume ($V = 30 \text{ m/s}$)

Table 4: Steam of Velocities Engineering Toolbox, (2003)

Steam System	Velocity	
	(m/s)	(ft/s)
Saturated Steam - high pressure	25 - 40	82 - 131
Saturated Steam - medium and low pressure	30-40	99 - 131
Saturated Steam at peak load	< 50	< 164
Steam and Water mix	< 25	< 82
Superheated Steam	35 - 100	100 - 300

Discussion and Analysis

Design Conditions

Following Design data is needed for designing any drying system

- Required drying temperature
- Amount of material to be dried per batch.
- Required drying time
- Steam condition

The internal condition is determined by the product or process, and there are as many possible specifications as there are different applications. The important point about the control level is that it must be specified in the absolute terms (kilogram) before any calculations can proceed. A steam ejector is able to draw a mass flow of flashed steam of 6Kg/second, obtained from specialist producer.

Operational parameters

- Steam ejector using steam at steam going in ($P = 2\text{bar}$) and ($T = 120$ degree) with velocity about 30m/s
- From the flash chamber, we remove flashed steam at a rate of 6 kg/second
- The vacuum condition needed is approximately 0.6 bar
- The outlet condenser vacuum is a little below atmosphere approximately 1bar

Figure 2: the design using vacuum drying and flash drying

So for our thinking, we going to propose the design using vacuum drying and flash drying like this. As shown in Figure,

Conclusion and Recommendation

Malaysia is one of the world's primary palm oil producer's In this study, the objective was to improve appropriate wastewater minimization and recycling technology which should be easy to operate and cost-effectively evaluate POME treatment at the source so as to reclaim water. The regulations followed during propose design using vacuum drying and flash drying, by using steam ejector the following points are the conclusion of this study.

The system integration will be formed by installing a flash dryer at the output of the sterilizer which will propose function to perform flash drying of POME as the output of sterilizer and possibly to reclaim water out of this POME.

Recommendations

Based on current information POME wastewater used for artificial recharge should receive at least secondary treatment.

This is critical to help ensure that water quality is maintained, to provide early warning of unexpected problems, and to help maintain the long term viability of the treatment system.

The price of recovered water should reflect the true cost of making the water available to ensure that the water is used efficiently. The costs of recharge operations should not be subsidized to make this water source more attractive than it would otherwise be.

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